

Synthesis and characterization of Ag₂S and Ag₂S/Ag₂(S,Se) NIR nanocrystals

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Introduction

Silver sulfide nanocrystals (Ag₂S NCs) have been used in the last few years in many research areas ranging from solar cells to biomedicine.^{1–7} Ag₂S NCs show some advantages such as emission in the second biological window (II-BW), where biomolecules and water show less light absorption,⁸ and low toxicity compared to other near-infrared (NIR) emitting NCs such as PbS or PbSe.⁹ Recently, the use of Ag₂S NCs as ratiometric nanothermometers has also been reported.¹⁰ However, their optical properties are still not fully understood, with reported photoluminescence (PL) emissions from 600 to 1250 nm for similar sized NCs.^{11–14}

In general, Ag₂S NCs synthesized in polar solvents show PL emissions much more energetic than those synthesized in non-polar media which emit at 1000–1250 nm (a thorough summary of the reported synthetic routes and their optical properties is given in Table S1,† section S1†). The disparity of results in the syntheses of these NCs demands revision and profuse analyses to rationally understand the formation mechanism of Ag₂S NCs and the relationship of the optical properties with their morphology and size.

Furthermore, from the first studies of Ag₂S NCs^{15–18} to the most recent ones,^{19,20} the heat-up syntheses using thiols yield NC arrangements of different sizes that form a non-stable colloid. Indeed, many authors have emphasized the difficulty in further using these metal-sulfide NCs due to a dense surface coating of different thiolated species, thus reducing their potential applications.^{21–25} The disaggregation of such NC arrangements is key to facilitate ligand exchange procedures and solution processability. In this work, we shed light on the chemistry behind the heat-up synthesis of Ag₂S NCs using silver(I) diethyldithiocarbamate (AgDDTC) and 1-dodecanethiol (DDT) and propose a hot-injection route to avoid the formation of such arrangements. This route yields isolated and stable Ag₂S NCs that can be further used as seeds to obtain Ag₂S/Ag₂(S,Se) NCs with improved optical properties upon a selenium treatment. As far as the authors know, no previous similar NCs have been described.^{19,22,26} The obtained hot-injection Ag₂S and Ag₂S/Ag₂(S,Se) NCs are easily transferable to water by simple ligand exchange procedures.

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Results and discussion

Fig. 1A shows a TEM image of Ag₂S NCs produced by a heat-up route in non-polar media using AgDDTC and DDT (route A, section S2†), where highly ordered aggregates are formed. These NCs have been previously studied by advanced microscopy and show a Ag-rich core.¹⁰ So far, these aggregates have been treated as self-assembled NCs due to the high monodispersity of the samples and the high degree of interdigitation and interaction between NCs.^{18,27} Fig. 1B shows the result of the here proposed hot-injection route (route B, section S2† for details), where, in contrast, isolated NCs are evident. These NCs consist of pure Ag₂S, as can be concluded from Fig. 1C showing the HRTEM image of four NCs. The distances and angles obtained from their FFT analysis correspond to the monoclinic acanthite Ag₂S phase (α -Ag₂S). Fig. 1E–

Fig. 1 (A) TEM images of Ag₂S NC aggregates produced by heat-up route (route A, S2†) and (B) disaggregated NCs obtained by the hot injection route (route B, S2†). (C) HRTEM images of Ag₂S NCs. Insets show the FFT performed on each NC. (D) Low magnification HAADF-STEM of Ag₂S NCs. (E–G) EDS elemental mapping showing the spatial distribution of (e) Ag (green), (F) S (orange), and (G) Ag and S of the set of NCs shown in (D). (H) Representative EDS spectrum of a NC. The corresponding X-ray intensity profiles extracted from the white arrow marked in image (G) are shown as an inset. (I) Atomic percentage of the previous intensity profile revealing the Ag₂S composition for the NCs.

F show the elemental mapping distribution of the HAADF-STEM image of Fig. 1D.

The homogeneous distribution of Ag and S is revealed by the analysis of the EDS spectrum (inset of Fig. 1H) across the NC marked with an arrow in Fig. 1G. The corresponding X-ray intensity profile shown in Fig. 1H as an inset, as well as the quantification of the intensity profile shown in Fig. 1I, confirm the presence of NCs with a composition close to the stoichiometric Ag₂S.

The isolation of the NC-aggregates has been possible by gaining insights into the chemistry of the NCs' formation by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, NMR. Fig. 2 compares the ¹H NMR spectra of (A) DDT, (B) a dispersion of Ag₂S NCs produced by heat-up route A with DDT and (C) silver(I) dodecanethiolate (Ag-DCT), a metal-organic polymeric product synthesized based on a previously reported procedure.²⁸

As evidenced, most of the signals present in the Ag₂S NC spectrum (B) are shared by the metal-organic polymeric product signals (C). The signals related to the protons in the α and β positions to the thiol group in the DDT spectrum (A) are at $\delta = 2.50$ ppm and $\delta = 1.60$ ppm, respectively (marked in grey). Bound DDT to colloidal quantum dots of different com-

Fig. 2 ¹H NMR spectra of (A) DDT, (B) NCs synthesized by heat-up route A and (C) the reaction intermediate (silver(I) dodecanethiolate). The signals marked in green correspond to dodecyl disulphide, in red to silver(I) dodecanethiolate and in grey to dodecanethiol. Signals marked with three, two and one star (*) correspond to residual toluene, acetone and water, respectively. The insets depict DDT (A), NCs-aggregates by the effect of Ag-DCT (B) and the polymer, Ag-DCT (C).

positions or CuInS₂ NCs is reported as a broad peak between 2.5 and 2.7 ppm.^{23,29}

The absence of these signals in the NC spectrum (B) discards the presence of DDT, free or anchored to the NC surface. The signals at 2.70 ppm and 1.65 ppm (marked in green), which are present both in the polymer (Ag-DCT) and the NC spectra are assigned to dodecyl disulfide, a well-known side product in the synthesis of metal sulfide NCs produced upon the oxidation of DDT.^{21,30}

Likewise, the Ag-DCT and the NC spectra share a triplet signal at 2.95 ppm related to the α -protons to the thiol group in the polymer. This signal, along with those related to dodecyl disulfide, is narrow and show multiplicity, suggesting that they are species that can be forming a part of the ligand shell but are not directly anchored to the surface. In contrast, in the spectra of the NCs, two additional broad signals centered at 1.95 and 3.10 ppm can be observed. Their width suggests a strong interaction with the NC surface, as confirmed by the Diffusion-Ordered Spectroscopy (DOSY) spectrum shown in Fig. 3. In this spectrum, two different sets of signals can be distinguished (apart from those coming from solvents): signals with diffusion coefficients far from bound species ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and two signals with diffusion coefficients of $1.4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, a reasonable value for tightly bound ligands to NC surfaces.³¹ The first set of signals is related to free Ag-DCT (at $\delta = 2.95 \text{ ppm}$) and dodecyl disulfide (at $\delta = 1.65$ and $\delta = 2.70 \text{ ppm}$). The second set of signals at $\delta = 3.10$ and $\delta = 1.95 \text{ ppm}$ is thus assigned to the Ag-DCT polymer. Applying the Stokes-Einstein relationship,³² the hydrodynamic diameter of these species is calculated to be

Fig. 3 DOSY spectrum of NCs synthesized by route A. From bottom to top, three sets of signals can be distinguished, corresponding to solvents, non-anchored species and anchored Ag-DCT to the NC surface, respectively.

5 nm, close to the size of the NCs observed in the TEM images (details in section S3†).

These findings, along with the aggregation observed in the TEM images, indicate that the main species anchored to the NC surface is the Ag-DCT polymer. Further evidence of the presence of this polymer during the synthesis of the Ag₂S NCs produced by route A is given by TEM and XRD measurements (section S4†). As previously reported, this polymer presents a lamellar structure, in which the silver atoms are located in plane, while the aliphatic chains of DDT are oriented perpendicular and interacting through van der Waals forces forming stacks of these lamellae with high thermal stability.^{28,33} The ability of metallic thiolates to embed other metal chalcogenide NCs has been observed for Cu_{2-x}S obtained from copper dodecanethiolate and octanethiolate²⁹ and recently, their role as templates for the formation of Cu₂Se and Ag₂Se nanowires through the calcination of their columnar phase has also been reported.³⁴ Thus, it seems plausible that Ag-DCT acts as a template in the here described synthesis of Ag₂S by heat-up route A.

Once the presence of this polymer on the surface of the NCs is confirmed, different synthetic strategies were followed to remove it and turn the NC solution processable. It was found that a combination of toluene and sulfur in oleylamine (OLA) is key to obtain isolated NCs as shown in Fig. 1B. The combination of these products was chosen because, on the one hand, toluene near its boiling point is the only known solvent for Ag-DCT.³⁵ On the other hand, the injection of sulfur in OLA at 100 °C rapidly produces H₂S,³⁶ causing the fast formation of metal sulfide NCs upon injection. The role of OLA in this synthesis is not only to activate sulfur to produce H₂S, but also to define the final surface chemistry of the NCs, as evidenced in the ¹H NMR spectra shown in Fig. 4, where the spectrum of OLA (Fig. 4A) is compared to that of NCs produced by route B (Fig. 4B). Indeed, OLA is found to bind to the surface of these NCs, as suggested by the broad peaks at $\delta = 5.3 \text{ ppm}$ and $\delta = 2.0 \text{ ppm}$ in the ¹H NMR spectrum marked in blue (Fig. 4B).

Fig. 4 ¹H NMR spectrum of (a) oleylamine and (b) NCs synthesized by the hot injection route (route B in section S2†).

In these samples, we can also observe narrow signals from dodecyl disulfide and free Ag-DCT, suggesting that these species might be intercalated between the anchored OLA ligands. However, no evidence for the broad signal at $\delta = 3.10$ ppm can be distinguished, confirming the absence of anchored Ag-DCT to the NC surface.

Due to the presence of OLA on the NC surface, the Ag_2S NCs obtained by this novel route (route B), free of the Ag-DCT polymer as a ligand, are easily ligand-exchangeable with water-soluble ligands like thiol-modified polyethylene glycol, providing bright water soluble NCs stable in solution for months (see section S5† for further TEM (Fig. S6†) and optical characterization of Ag_2S NCs in tetrachloroethylene (TCE) and water (Fig. S7†)). The evidence for a better ligand exchange process due to the presence of OLA passivating the NCs was obtained by ICP-MS. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that when route A NCs are exposed to a ligand exchange procedure, only 15% of the silver mass in the NCs is transferred to water. However, when route B NCs are exposed to the same ligand exchange procedure, 67% of them end up in the aqueous phase. Thus, it is clear that the elimination of the dense coating of the polymer is a major advantage for post-reaction treatments of the NCs. Disaggregation and good colloidal stability provided by this route not only allow easier ligand exchange, but also further control of their optical properties by post-synthetic procedures, as shown in Fig. 5A, showing the absorption and emission spectra of Ag_2S NCs and NCs treated with Se ($\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs from now on). In particular, the addition of Se in a quantity equivalent to the growth of roughly a monolayer of Ag_2Se on the surface of the NCs (through a solution of Se@TOP, see details in S2†) yields

Table 1 Amount of Ag_2S NCs transferred to water depending on the synthetic procedure

	Ag^+ mass in chloroform (mg)	Ag^+ mass in water (mg)	Yield (%)
Route A NCs	1.923 ± 0.008	0.282 ± 0.005	15
Route B NCs	1.536 ± 0.004	1.022 ± 0.001	67

Fig. 5 (A) Absorption and photoluminescence of the as-synthesized Ag_2S (black) and $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs (red) for the same value of O.D. = 0.1 at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 822$ nm in tetrachloroethylene, TCE. (B) Comparison between the PL of commercially available NCs (blue) and the ones synthesized in this work: Ag_2S (black) and $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ (red) at O.D. = 0.1 at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 822$ nm in water.

NCs with improved optical properties while maintaining their size distribution and stability. The improved optical properties are presumably due to the passivation of surface trap states.

Furthermore and importantly, according to its ^1H NMR spectrum (Fig. S9†), this growth step in the presence of Se does not modify the ligand sphere of the NCs, allowing for similar ligand exchange procedures as the one developed for the previously described Ag_2S NCs. (Section S6† for TEM and optical characterization.) The addition of more Se does not generate an improvement in their optical properties but lowers their colloidal stability due to unreacted Se@TOP.

The measurement of the photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) in the NIR region is challenging due to the lower sensitivity of the infrared detectors compared to the visible range ones, and due to the instability of the NIR emitting dyes like those commonly used (IR-125 and IR-26).³⁵ Moreover, the PLQY of IR-26, that is taken as a standard, has been recently reviewed after accurate measurements with an integrating sphere.^{37,38} This method has the advantage of measuring directly the amount of absorbed and emitted photons by the whole sample, which results in more accurate values than other methods such as dynamics measurements³⁹ because it considers physical limitations like reabsorption.⁴⁰ For this reason, the absolute PLQY of all the samples synthesized in this work was measured using an integrating sphere. Details of the procedure are described elsewhere.⁴⁰

The PLQY of the here studied samples in TCE is 2.5% (for route A NCs), 0.24% (for route B NCs) and 0.65% for $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs. These differences between route A (heat-up) and route B (hot-injection) NCs may be related to different factors including different synthesis temperatures (around 200 °C for heat-up NCs and 100 °C for hot-injection ones), NC size (smaller in general for heat-up NCs) and ligand density. As comparison, in the case of the NCs synthesized by route A, the reported PLQY obtained after ligand exchange is around 10–15% when measured using the dye IR-26 (see Table 1, section S1†). In our case, measured with the integrating sphere, similar samples gave a QY in tetrachloroethylene (TCE) of 2.5%, which is around 5 times lower than the one obtained using the dye, making it difficult to compare the yields from these two different methods.

For this reason, in order to confirm the potential use of the NCs in aqueous media, their PL was compared to commercially available Ag_2S NCs in water. As shown in Fig. 5B for the same value of O.D. (0.1) and excitement at the same wavelength (822 nm), the PL emission intensity of water soluble $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs is more than double than that of the commercial ones, while water soluble Ag_2S NCs (route B) shows less intensity. While higher values are desirable, recent studies show that the PLQYs of these NCs are sufficient to perform optical studies *in vivo*.⁴¹ Thus, the benefit of the here described $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs is twofold: improvement in optical properties with respect to Ag_2S ones and the possibility to transfer into water much higher amounts of NCs in one single procedure, saving ligand and time. This allows the

production of concentrated samples with a higher PL signal than commercially available NCs from one single batch.

In order to elucidate the incorporation of Se in the Ag_2S matrix (its location on the surface or in the volume), EDX and EELS studies were performed. However, due to the low quantity of Se in the samples, EDX mapping was not able to properly resolve the structure. For this reason, XAS studies, including XANES (X-Ray Absorption Near Edge Structure) and EXAFS (Extended X-Ray Absorption Fine Structure), were performed.

The results at the Ag L_3 - and S K-edges can be seen in Fig. 6A and B for Ag_2S NCs before and after ligand exchange and with and without Se. As can be seen in Fig. 6A, the XANES spectra, at the Ag L_3 -edge in the Total Electron Yield (TEY) mode, are almost identical in all samples. The same results are obtained from the signal acquired in the fluorescence mode (not shown here). The shape of these spectra is also similar to those that are present for reference materials, Ag_2S and Ag_2Se ,⁴² and for silver NPs capped with DDT.⁴³ Thus, a clear identification of the formed species is not straightforward in the silver edge.

XANES spectra at the S K-edge obtained in the TEY mode (Fig. 6B) show a main contribution at 2473 eV (vertical solid line) associated with the presence of S^{2-} in all samples. Ag_2S NCs after ligand exchange (denoted as Ag_2S hydrophilic NCs, red line), show other two resonances at 2476 eV (vertical dashed line) and 2481 eV (vertical dashed-dotted line), corresponding to the presence of sulfur with valence states +4, and a mixture of +5 and +6, respectively. It is worth noting that these resonances do not appear in the hydrophilic sample treated with Se ($\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs transferred to water) and were not observed in any of the samples when the absorption signal is

Fig. 6 XANES spectra of the studied Ag_2S samples before and after ligand exchange, and with and without Se, performed in the TEY mode at the Ag L_3 -edge (A) and the S K-edge (B). (C) XANES spectra of the studied Ag_2S samples before and after ligand exchange, and with and without Se, performed in the fluorescence mode at the S K-edge. (D) XANES spectra of the $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ sample, performed in the fluorescence mode at the Se K-edge.

Fig. 7 (A) k^2 -Weighted Fourier transform of the EXAFS oscillation for the $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs (black line), simulated spectra obtained using the FEFF code for Ag_2Se (green line) and SeS_2 (blue line). (B) k^2 -Weighted Fourier transform of the EXAFS oscillation for $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs (circles), together with the fitting models proposed: one shell Se–Ag (red line) and two shells Se–Ag and Se–S (green line).

obtained in the fluorescence mode (Fig. 6C), being in this last case where all the signals were measured corresponding to S^{2-} . The TEY mode is sensitive to the surface atom's state, while the fluorescence mode is volume sensitive, giving an averaged information from the whole NC. The comparison of both spectra shows that the Se atoms are located on the surface of the NCs, preventing the oxidation of S when the sample is in aqueous media. This extra layer is not only favouring the PLQY of the NCs but is also acting as a protection layer that isolates their surface from the air oxidation improving their long-term stability. However, the XANES spectra do not provide any information about the chemical state of Se at the Ag and S absorption edges due to the difference in the concentration of Ag and S compared to the one of the Se. For this reason, XAS measurements (XANES and EXAFS) were performed at the Se K-edge. The XANES region performed in the fluorescence mode (Fig. 6D) for Ag_2S NCs treated with Se@TOP shows all the features present in the spectrum corresponding to the Ag_2Se reference sample,⁴⁴ and is completely different from the spectrum of metallic Se, so the presence of Se^0 covering the NCs can be discarded.

The Se atomic distribution in the Se treated NCs was analysed by probing the local structure around Se atoms by EXAFS. This technique provides structural information of both homogeneous and non-homogeneous nanomaterials by the analysis of the fitted averaged coordination numbers and interatomic distances.⁴⁵ Fig. 7A shows the magnitude of the Fourier Transform (FT) of the EXAFS oscillation obtained at the Se K-edge, and simulated spectra using the FEFF code⁴⁶ for Ag_2Se and SeS_2 . The FT of the sample presents two principal peaks at 1.8 Å and 2.5 Å (without phase correction).

These contributions are approximately in the same positions as those obtained for the Ag_2Se structure, in accordance with the XANES results. We can observe a difference in the

intensity ratio between these peaks, being roughly 1/2 for the studied sample, and roughly 1/3 for the theoretical structure of Ag_2Se (see Fig. 7A). This difference can be attributed to the presence of some S atoms in the neighbourhood of Se.

To verify this hypothesis, two fit models were proposed; the first one considers only one shell around the Se atoms composed of atoms of Ag. The result of the fit is shown in Fig. 7B (red line), and as it can be seen, its quality is not good enough, especially for the first peak. The second model, adding a new coordination shell for Se, containing S atoms, shows a much better fitting result (Fig. 7B (green line) and Table S2,† section S7†).

The Ag_2Se alloy has seven Ag atoms as first neighbours of the Se ones, with interatomic distances ($R_{\text{Se-Ag}}$) between 2.7 and 2.9 Å. For the sample treated with Se, the average coordination number ($N_{\text{Se-Ag}}$) obtained from the fit ($N_{\text{Se-Ag}} = 2.8$, see Table S2,† section S7†) is lower than expected (*i.e.* seven Ag atoms), and also the presence of some S atoms in the structure is needed to improve the quality of the fit (Fig. 7B). The presence of some S atoms in the structure would lead to a reduction in the $N_{\text{Se-Ag}}$, but this could not fully explain the reduction found. On the other hand, the reduction in the $N_{\text{Se-Ag}}$ can be a consequence of both, the nanometric size of the NCs and the superficial location of Se in the NCs. Indeed, these Se atoms on the surface of a NC contribute to a lower $N_{\text{Se-Ag}}$ than that in the bulk. Thus, for a NC of about 8 nm in diameter (according to TEM measurements, see Fig. S12†), a reduction of less than 5% in the $N_{\text{Se-Ag}}$ can be expected. Since in these NCs the decrease is higher (60%), to explain this additional reduction for the $N_{\text{Se-Ag}}$, it is necessary that the Se atoms form a $\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ structure, preferably in a thin layer (less than 1 nm) over the surface of the Ag_2S NCs.

Conclusions

In conclusion, NMR studies have allowed identifying the presence of silver(I) dodecanethiolate, a polymer that forms during the synthesis of Ag_2S NCs by heat-up routes in the presence of thiols. This route produces well-ordered NC aggregates with poor colloidal stability and reduced processability, as this polymer hinders effective ligand-exchange procedures to make the NCs water-soluble.

The development of a novel synthetic route allows obtaining Ag_2S NCs with increased versatility allowing for much more efficient ligand exchange procedures, and further growth of a $\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ outer layer, as resolved by advance synchrotron XAS spectroscopy. $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ NCs show improved chemical stability compared to core-only NCs and improved optical properties compared to commercially available Ag_2S NCs.

Author contributions

Diego Ruiz is the main contributor to this work and performed the synthesis, steady-state optical characterization, XRD, TEM

and NMR experiments under the supervision of Beatriz H. Juarez, who led the research. Martín Mizrahi and Felix G. Requejo performed the synchrotron measurements and contributed to the X-ray absorption spectroscopy information. Callum M. S. Jones and José Marqués-Hueso performed the quantum yield measurements in an integration sphere. Almudena Torres-Pardo and José M. González-Calbet were in charge of the advanced HRTEM inspections in the aberration corrected microscope. Harrison D. A. Santos performed the optical characterization under the supervision of Daniel Jaque and Carlos Jacinto. All authors contributed to the written text.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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References

- 1 T. Yang, Y. A. Tang, L. Liu, X. Lv, Q. Wang, H. Ke, Y. Deng, H. Yang, X. Yang, G. Liu, Y. Zhao and H. Chen, *ACS Nano*, 2017, **11**, 1848–1857.
- 2 S. Li, L. Xu, M. Sun, X. Wu, L. Liu, H. Kuang and C. Xu, *Adv. Mater.*, 2017, **29**, 1606086.
- 3 X. Zhang, M. Liu, H. Liu and S. Zhang, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2014, **56**, 307–312.
- 4 G. Chen, F. Tian, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhang, C. Li and Q. Wang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2013, **24**, 2481–2488.

- 5 J. Amaya Suárez, J. J. Plata, A. M. Márquez and J. Fernández Sanz, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2017, **121**, 7290–7296.
- 6 M. Jagadeeswararao, A. Swarnkar, G. B. Markad and A. Nag, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2016, **120**, 19461–19469.
- 7 S. Lin, Y. Feng, X. Wen, T. Harada, T. W. Kee, S. Huang, S. Shrestha and G. Conibeer, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2016, **120**, 10199–10205.
- 8 A. M. Smith, M. C. Mancini and S. Nie, *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, 2009, **4**, 710–711.
- 9 F. Hu, C. Li, Y. Zhang, M. Wang, D. Wu and Q. Wang, *Nano Res.*, 2015, **8**, 1637–1647.
- 10 D. Ruiz, B. del Rosal, M. Acebrón, C. Palencia, C. Sun, J. Cabanillas-González, M. López-Haro, A. B. Hungria, D. Jaque and B. H. Juárez, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2017, **27**, 1604629.
- 11 Y. Du, B. Xu, T. Fu, M. Cai, F. Li, Y. Zhang and Q. Wang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 1470–1471.
- 12 R. Gui, A. Wan, X. Liu, W. Yuan and H. Jin, *Nanoscale*, 2014, **6**, 5467–5473.
- 13 Y. Zhang, Y. Liu, C. Li, X. Chen and Q. Wang, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2014, **118**, 4918–4923.
- 14 R. Ahmad, R. Srivastava, H. Bhardwaj, S. Yadav, V. Nand Singh, S. Chand, N. Singh and S. Sapra, *ChemistrySelect*, 2018, **3**, 5620–5629.
- 15 L. Motte, F. Billoudet and M. P. Pileni, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1995, **99**, 16425–16429.
- 16 A. Taleb, C. Petit and M. P. Pileni, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1998, **102**, 2214–2220.
- 17 L. Motte, F. Billoudet, E. Lacaze, J. Douin and M. P. Pileni, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1997, **101**, 138–144.
- 18 M. P. Pileni, L. Motte, F. Billoudet, J. Mahrt and F. Willig, *Mater. Lett.*, 1997, **31**, 255–260.
- 19 S. Shen, Y. Zhang, L. Peng, Y. Du and Q. Wang, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 7115–7118.
- 20 Z. Zhuang, X. Lu, Q. Peng and Y. Li, *Chem. – Eur. J.*, 2011, **17**, 10445–10452.
- 21 M. J. Turo and J. E. Macdonald, *ACS Nano*, 2014, **8**, 10205–10213.
- 22 R. Xie, M. Rutherford and X. Peng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 5691–5697.
- 23 M. Gromova, A. Lefrançois, L. Vaure, F. Agnese, D. Aldakov, A. Maurice, D. Djurado, C. Lebrun, A. de Geyer, T. U. Schüllli, S. Pouget and P. Reiss, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2017, **139**, 15748–15759.
- 24 Z. Pan, I. Mora-Seró, Q. Shen, H. Zhang, Y. Li, K. Zhao, J. Wang, X. Zhong and J. Bisquert, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **136**, 9203–9210.
- 25 C. H. M. van Oversteeg, F. E. Oropeza, J. P. Hofmann, E. J. M. Hensen, P. E. de Jongh and C. de Mello Donega, *Chem. Mater.*, 2019, **31**, 541–552.
- 26 M. Bernechea, N. C. Miller, G. Xercavins, D. So, A. Stavrinadis and G. Konstantatos, *Nat. Photonics*, 2016, **10**, 521.
- 27 L. Motte, F. Billoudet, E. Lacaze and M.-P. Pileni, *Adv. Mater.*, 1996, **8**, 1018–1020.
- 28 I. G. Dance, K. J. Fisher, R. M. H. Banda and M. L. Scudder, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 183–187.
- 29 M. Acebrón, J. F. Galisteo-López, D. Granados, J. López-Ogalla, J. M. Gallego, R. Otero, C. López and B. H. Juárez, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2015, **7**, 6935–6945.
- 30 P. Reiss, M. Carrière, C. Lincheneau, L. Vaure and S. Tamang, *Chem. Rev.*, 2016, **116**, 10731–10819.
- 31 B. Fritzing, R. K. Capek, K. Lambert, J. C. Martins and Z. Hens, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 10195–10201.
- 32 Z. Hens and J. C. Martins, *Chem. Mater.*, 2013, **25**, 1211–1221.
- 33 Z. Ye, L. P. de la Rama, M. Y. Efremov, J.-M. Zuo and L. H. Allen, *Dalton Trans.*, 2016, **45**, 18954–18966.
- 34 W. Bryks, S. C. Smith and A. R. Tao, *Chem. Mater.*, 2017, **29**, 3653–3662.
- 35 A. A. Levchenko, C. K. Yee, A. N. Parikh and A. Navrotsky, *Chem. Mater.*, 2005, **17**, 5428–5438.
- 36 J. W. Thomson, K. Nagashima, P. M. Macdonald and G. A. Ozin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 5036–5041.
- 37 O. E. Semonin, J. C. Johnson, J. M. Luther, A. G. Midgett, A. J. Nozik and M. C. Beard, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **1**, 2445–2450.
- 38 S. Hatami, C. Würth, M. Kaiser, S. Leubner, S. Gabriel, L. Bahrig, V. Lesnyak, J. Pauli, N. Gaponik, A. Eychmüller and U. Resch-Genger, *Nanoscale*, 2015, **7**, 133–143.
- 39 A. Penzkofer, O. Lammel and T. Tsuboi, *Opt. Commun.*, 2002, **214**, 305–313.
- 40 A. Boccolini, J. Marques-Hueso, D. Chen, Y. Wang and B. S. Richards, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, 2014, **122**, 8–14.
- 41 B. del Rosal, D. Ruiz, I. Chaves-Coira, B. H. Juárez, L. Monge, G. Hong, N. Fernández and D. Jaque, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2018, **28**, 1806088.
- 42 Y. L. Mikhlin, G. A. Pal'yanova, Y. V. Tomashevich, E. A. Vishnyakova, S. A. Vorobyev and K. A. Kokh, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 2018, **116**, 292–298.
- 43 J. D. Padmos and P. Zhang, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2012, **116**, 23094–23101.
- 44 E. Nakazawa, T. Ikemoto, A. Hokura, Y. Terada, T. Kunito, T. Yamamoto, T. K. Yamada, F. C. W. Rosas, G. Fillmann, S. Tanabe and I. Nakai, *J. Environ. Monit.*, 2011, **13**, 1678–1686.
- 45 A. I. Frenkel, A. Yevick, C. Cooper and R. Vasic, *Annu. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 2011, **4**, 23–39.
- 46 J. J. Rehr, J. J. Kas, F. D. Vila, M. P. Prange and K. Jorissen, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2010, **12**, 5503–5513.

Synthesis and characterization of Ag₂S and Ag₂S/Ag₂(S,Se) NIR nanocrystals

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Section S1. Summary of the synthetic routes and the optical properties reported for Ag₂S NCs

Route	Silver precursor	Sulfur precursor	Solvent	Ligand(s)	Synthesis T (°C)	PL (nm)	PLQY	PL lifetime/ns	Ref.
Heat-up	AgDDTC	DT	DT	DT	200	975-1175	not shown	57-181	1
Heat-up	AgDDTC	DT	DT	DT, PEG-DHLA	200	1200	15.5% (water)	not shown	2
Heat-up	AgDDTC	DT	DT	DT, C18PMH-PEG	150	1100	17% (water)	61	3
Heat-up	AgDDTC	DT	ODE	DT, DSPE-PEG ₂₀₀₀	170	1170	4.48% (water)	not shown	4
Heat-up	AgDDTC	AgDDTC	ODE	OA, ODA	200	1058	not shown	not shown	5
Heat-up	AgDDTC	DT	ODE	DT, polypeptide gels	140	1100	5.1% (organic), 4.3% (water)	not shown	6
Heat-up	AgAc	DT	ODE	OLA	250	1250	not shown	not shown	7
Hot injection	AgAc	TMS	OT	OT	165	1150	4.5% (hexane)	not shown	8
Seeded growth	AgAc, AgOA	TMS	ODE, TOL	MA, OA	50-110	700-1250	0.18% (hexane), 0.15% (water)	57	9
Heat-up	AgOA	DT	ODE, OA	DT	220	1250	not shown	not shown	10
Hot injection	NHC-AgBr	TMS	CH ₂ Cl ₂ , ODE	NHC	RT	not shown	not shown	not shown	11
Hot injection	AgCl	(NH ₄) ₂ S	TOP	OLA	30	980	not shown	not shown	12
Heat-up	AgSCOPh	AgSCOPh	TOP, HDA, OCTA, DOA, EDA	HDA, OCTA, DOA, EDA	80-120	not shown	not shown	not shown	13
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	S in TOL	TOL	OCTA	RT	1000-1250	not shown	not shown	14
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	TAA in OLA	TOP	OLA	100	800	not shown	56.4	15
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	3-MPA	EG	3-MPA	145	510-1210	2.1% (water)	not shown	16
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	Na ₂ S	H ₂ O	BSA	37	650-850	0.75%-1.8% (water)	728	17
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	Na ₂ S	H ₂ O	2-MPA	30-90	786-950	14-39% (water)	not shown	18
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	Na ₂ S	H ₂ O	HSA	55	1060	1.26-1.32% (water)	not shown	19
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	S in NH ₂ -NH ₂	H ₂ O	GSH	RT	620	1.9% (water)	not shown	20
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	S in NH ₂ -NH ₂	H ₂ O	GSH	20	600-760	0.1-1.2% (water)	not shown	21
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	S in TOP	ODE	OA, ODA, TOP	150	not shown	not shown	not shown	22
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	DMSA	H ₂ O	DMSA	70-90	780-920	6.3-6.5% (water)	not shown	23
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	S in NH ₂ -NH ₂	H ₂ O	Multidentate polymers	95	687-1096	14.2-16.4% (water)	not shown	24
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	DT	DT	DT	200	not shown	not shown	not shown	25
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	S powder	ODA	ODA	170	not shown	not shown	not shown	26
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	TAA	OLA	OLA	210	1200	not shown	not shown	27
Hot injection	AgNO ₃	Na ₂ S	H ₂ O	MPEG-SH	90	775-930	1.9-65.6% (water)	not shown	28
Heat-up	AgNO ₃	DPA	H ₂ O	DPA	Micro wave IR	639-802	0.72-2.7% (water)	816	29

Abbreviations: DHLA: Dihydrolipoic acid, C18PMH-PEG: Poly(maleic anhydride-alt-1-octadecene)-polyethylene glycol, DSPE: distearoylphosphatidylethanolamine-poly(ethylene glycol), ODA: Octadecylamine, OA: Oleic acid, OLA: Oleylamine, TMS: bis(trimethylsilyl) sulfide, OT: 1-octanethiol, AgAc: Silver (I) acetate, AgOA: Silver (I) oleate, TOL: Toluene, MA: Myristic acid, NHC-AgBr: N-heterocyclic carbene-silver bromide, TOP: Trioctylphosphine, AgSCOPh: Silver (I) thiobenzoate, HDA: Hexadecylamine, OCTA: Octylamine, DOA: Dioctylamine, EDA: Ethylenediamine, 3-MPA: 3-mercaptopropionic acid, EG: Ethylene glycol, BSA: Bovine serum albumin, 2-MPA: 2-mercaptopropionic acid, HSA: Human serum albumin, DMSA: Dimercaptosuccinic acid, TAA: Thioacetamide, MPEG-SH: Thiol modified polyethylene glycol, DPA: D-penicillamine.

Table S1. Synthetic routes reported for Ag₂S NCs

Section S2. Experimental section

Chemicals: Silver (I) diethyldithiocarbamate (AgDDTC, 99%), 1-dodecanethiol (DT, >98%), toluene (TOL, 99.8%), acetone (technical grade), oleylamine (OLA, 70%), sulfur powder (S, synthesis grade), polyethylene glycol methyl ether thiol (PEG-SH, average M_n 6000), chloroform (CHCl_3 , >99.8%), tetrachloroethylene (TCE, >99%), trioctylamine (TOA, 98%), silver (I) nitrate (AgNO_3 , >99.0%), acetonitrile (99.8%), deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3 , 99.8% D), hexane (reagent grade), ethanol (EtOH, 96%), selenium powder (Se, 99.99%) and trioctylphosphine (TOP, 97%). All chemicals were used without further purification. The commercial Ag_2S -PEG-COOH NCs were purchased from NIR-optics technologies, China.

Syntheses of Ag_2S NCs by heat-up routes (route A):

For the synthesis of these NCs the route followed was the one by Zhang et al.² Briefly, 0.1 mmol of AgDDTC was added along with 10 mg of DT in a three neck round bottom flask. The mixture was heated to 200°C and left to react for an hour. The NCs were washed with ethanol and toluene.

Syntheses of Ag_2S NCs by hot injection (route B):

In this case, 0.2 mmol of AgDDTC, 60 mmol of DT and 10 ml of toluene were mixed in a three neck round bottom flask. The mixture was heated to 100°C and when the silver salt is completely dissolved and the solution turns to a bright yellow color 100 μL of a solution of 0.4 mmol of sulfur powder in 1 ml of OLA is swiftly injected. The solution is then left to react until it is quenched using a water bath. The content is passed to a plastic centrifuge tube and precipitated with acetone.

These NCs were found to be very stable in the reaction media, so several cycles of centrifugation at 9000 rpm and cooling of the centrifuge tube were necessary to precipitate all the NCs. The addition of ethanol has a positive influence in the destabilization of the NCs but it was also found to irrevocably quench the NCs PL almost completely. Typically, the washing steps were carried out using the same amount of acetone as the reaction media and a few drops of ethanol if the NCs were too stable to precipitate.

Syntheses of $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ NCs:

For the synthesis of these NCs: 0.2 mmol of AgDDTC, 60 mmol of DT and 10 ml of toluene were mixed in a three neck round bottom flask. The mixture was heated to 100°C and when the silver salt is completely dissolved and the solution turns to a bright yellow color 100 μL of a solution of 0.4 mmol of sulfur powder in 1 ml of OLA is swiftly injected.

After 5 minutes 100 μL of a 1 M solution of Se powder in TOP is injected into the NCs dispersion. The solution is left to react for 10 minutes and then, it is left to naturally cool to room temperature. The washing steps were carried out with acetone and chloroform.

Ligand exchange reactions:

All batches are dispersed in 10 ml of chloroform and from that solution, 1 ml of NCs ($[\text{Ag}^+] \cong 1.5 \text{ mg/ml}$) is added to a 5 ml chloroform solution containing 100 mg of PEG-SH. The mixture is sonicated at room temperature for half an hour and then is left in a mechanical agitator for 1.5 h. After that, the chloroform is blown dry using a N_2 flow and 5-10 ml of ethanol is added to the NCs deposit. The solution is vortexed and sonicated until an optically clear dispersion is obtained. In order to remove the excess polymer two centrifugation steps were followed with ethanol using Sartorius Vivaspin 20 MWCO= 100 KDa ultracentrifugation tubes. After that, three cycles of centrifugation and redispersion in water were found to be enough to eliminate the ethanol and the remaining polymer. The NCs obtained using this method were stable in the water dispersion for months in storage at 4°C.

In order to compare the behavior of the two kinds of NCs in ligands exchange reactions, aliquots with the same quantity of Ag^+ (measured by ICP-MS) were subjected to the above procedure. The amount of NCs transferred to water were measured as the quantity of Ag^+ detected in the water samples measured using ICP-MS.

Photoluminescence Quantum Yield measurements

Fluorescence spectra were obtained using a calibrated spectrofluorometer (Edinburgh Instruments, FLS920), with a xenon lamp as excitation source, an integrating sphere (Jobin-Yvon), and a liquid nitrogen cooled NIR photo-multiplier tube (Hamamatsu, R5509-72).

Synchrotron measurements

X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) experiments were performed at the SXS (S K- and Ag L_3 - edges) and XAFS2 (Se K-edge) beamlines at the LNLS (Laboratório Nacional de Luz Síncrotron), Campinas, Brazil.

X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES) spectroscopy measurements at the S K-edge (2472 eV) and Ag L_3 -edge (3351 eV) were carried out using a InSb(111) double-crystal monochromator, giving an energy resolution of 2 eV at the S K-edge, and 1 eV at the Ag L_3 -edge. Experiments with soft X-rays were performed in a vacuum chamber at 10^{-9} mbar and room temperature

(RT). The incident beam intensity (I_0) was measured using a thin foil of Al. Samples were dropped on carbon tapes to be measured in Total Electron Yield (TEY) and Fluorescence (FL) modes simultaneously. The photon energies were calibrated using a Mo and Ag metallic foil setting the first inflection point of the Mo L_3 absorption edge at 2520 eV for S, and to the Ag L_3 absorption edge (3351 eV) for Ag measurements. The final XANES spectra were obtained after background subtraction and normalization to the postedge intensity.

XANES and Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS) experiments at the Se K-edge (12658 eV) were measured at room temperature using a Si(111) single channel-cut crystal monochromator in fluorescence mode. An ionization chamber was used to detect the incident flux and a 15-element germanium solid-state detector was used to sense the fluorescence signal from the sample. The EXAFS data was extracted from the measured absorption spectra by standard methods using the ATHENA software which is part of the Demeter package.³⁰ The Fourier transforms were calculated using the Hanning filtering function. EXAFS modeling was carried out using the ARTEMIS program (Demeter package). Structural parameters (coordination numbers, interatomic distances and Debye–Waller factor) were obtained by nonlinear least-squares fit of the theoretical EXAFS signal to the data in R space by Fourier Transforming both the experimental and calculated data. Theoretical scattering path amplitudes and phase shifts for all paths used on the fits and simulations were calculated using the FEFF code.³¹ The passive reduction factor S_0^2 was restrained to the value of 0.72. This value was obtained fitting the EXAFS spectrum of metallic Se foil and constraining the coordination number of the first coordination shell to 2.

NMR experiments

NMR samples were thoroughly washed and dried using a N₂ flux to minimize the signals of the solvent and non-solvent used in the washing steps. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Avance II 300 MHz spectrometer. DOSY experiments were recorded using a Bruker Avanced III-HD NANOBAV 300 MHz with diffusion time of 250 ms and a variable gradient length.

TEM characterization:

Figures 1A and 1B were acquired in a JEOL 1010 operating at 100 kV. Images 1C-1I were acquired in an aberration-corrected JEOL-JEM ARM300cF microscope operating at 80 kV in order to minimize the electron beam damage.

Section S3. Characterization of route A NCs

Figure S1. TEM image and size distribution of the route A as-synthesized Ag₂S NCs

Figure S2. Steady-state absorption and PL of the route A, Ag₂S NCs

Figure S3. XRD diffractogram of the Ag₂S NCs synthesized by route A

Section S4. Identification of the $\text{AgSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$ polymer during the course of the reaction

Isolation of the intermediate silver compound: In order to isolate the chemical compound that undergoes the decomposition to Ag_2S a mixture of 0.2 mmol of AgDDTC , 60 mmol of DT and 10 ml of toluene is heated to 100°C in a three neck round bottom flask. When the silver salt is completely dissolved and the reaction media presents a bright yellow color the reaction is quenched using a water bath. Upon cooling, the reaction starts to present turbidity and a darker color, due a partial decomposition of the precursor. The white solid is isolated from the reddish liquid by centrifugation and washed with hexane. Figure S4 compares a TEM image of this product with the NCs aggregates obtained by the heat-up route (route A).

Figure S4. a) TEM image of $\text{AgSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$ lamellae isolated from the reaction media and b) Aggregates of Ag_2S NCs synthesized by

heat-up route A.

The presence of the $\text{AgSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$ in the reaction media was confirmed also using a series of XRD experiments. Figure S5 compares the XRD diffractogram of the starting silver salt, AgDDTC , with the XRD of the intermediate isolated from the heat-up reaction and the polymer $\text{AgSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$ synthesized as described below. It can be seen that the peaks of the intermediate match clearly with those of the lamellar structure of the silver polymer, and are significantly different from those corresponding to the initial salt precursor.

Synthesis of $\text{AgSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$: The synthesis of the silver polymer was carried out based on a previously reported procedure.³² A solution of 1 mmol of AgNO_3 in 5 ml of acetonitrile is slowly injected into a solution of 2 mmol of 1-dodecanethiol and 2 mmol of trioctylamine in 10 ml of acetonitrile. The $\text{AgSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$ is formed immediately upon the injection of the silver solution. The white powder is washed by centrifugation in hexane to eliminate the excess products and dried using an oven at 50°C .

Figure S5. XRD diffractograms of the AgDDTC , $\text{AgSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$ and the reaction intermediate

Section S5. Characterization of the Ag₂S NCs synthesized by route B

Figure S6. TEM and HRTEM images of Ag₂S NCs synthesized by route B at different magnifications

Figure S7. a) Optical extinction and photoluminescence spectra of different aliquots of Ag₂S NCs with different sizes (specified in the legend) and b) optical absorption and photoluminescence spectra before (dark red) and after (dark blue) the ligand exchange procedure described in section S2. Red line corresponds to NCs in tetrachloroethylene (TCE) and blue line for NCs transferred to water.

Figure S8. XRD diffractogram of the Ag₂S NCs synthesized by route B

Section S6. Characterization of $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ NCs

Figure S9. ^1H NMR spectra of a) OLA, b) route B Ag_2S NCs, and c) $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ NCs.

Figure S10. TEM images of the as-synthesized $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ NCs.

Figure S11. a) Photoluminescence spectra of aliquots of the $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ NCs at different reaction times after the Se@TOP injection and b) Absorption and photoluminescence spectra of the NCs before (dark blue) and after the ligand exchange procedure (dark red).

Figure S12. Size distribution of the as-synthesized $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Ag}_2(\text{S,Se})$ NCs

Section S7. Structural parameters from EXAFS analysis of the Se K-edge

Sample	N _{Se-Ag}	R _{Se-Ag} (Å)	DWF _{Se-Ag} (Å ²)	N _{Se-S}	R _{Se-S} (Å)	DWF _{Se-S} (Å ²)
(Ag ₂ S/Ag ₂ (S,Se) NCs	2.8(4)	2.6 - 2.8	0.010(3)	1.0(4)	2.10(4)	0.06(1)
Ag ₂ S standard	7	2.7 - 2.9				

Table S2. Fitted structural parameters (N: average coordination number; R: interatomic distance; DWF: Debye-Waller factor) obtained from the EXAFS analysis using a two-shell model.

References

1. Y. Zhang, Y. Liu, C. Li, X. Chen and Q. Wang, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 2014, **118**, 4918-4923.
2. Y. Zhang, G. Hong, Y. Zhang, G. Chen, F. Li, H. Dai and Q. Wang, *ACS Nano*, 2012, **6**, 3695-3702.
3. F. Hu, C. Li, Y. Zhang, M. Wang, D. Wu and Q. Wang, *Nano Research*, 2015, **8**, 1637-1647.
4. M.-Y. Qin, X.-Q. Yang, K. Wang, X.-S. Zhang, J.-T. Song, M.-H. Yao, D.-M. Yan, B. Liu and Y.-D. Zhao, *Nanoscale*, 2015, **7**, 19484-19492.
5. Y. Du, B. Xu, T. Fu, M. Cai, F. Li, Y. Zhang and Q. Wang, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2010, **132**, 1470-1471.
6. D.-H. Zhao, J. Yang, R.-X. Xia, M.-H. Yao, R.-M. Jin, Y.-D. Zhao and B. Liu, *Chemical Communications*, 2018, **54**, 527-530.
7. P.-J. Wu, J.-W. Yu, H.-J. Chao and J.-Y. Chang, *Chemistry of Materials*, 2014, **26**, 3485-3494.
8. H. He, Y. Lin, Z. Q. Tian, D. L. Zhu, Z. L. Zhang and D. W. Pang, *Small*, 2018, **14**, 1703296.
9. P. Jiang, Z.-Q. Tian, C.-N. Zhu, Z.-L. Zhang and D.-W. Pang, *Chemistry of Materials*, 2012, **24**, 3-5.
10. P. Li, Q. Peng and Y. Li, *Chemistry – A European Journal*, 2010, **17**, 941-946.
11. H. Lu and R. L. Brutchey, *Chemistry of Materials*, 2017, **29**, 1396-1403.
12. H. Zhang, B.-R. Hyun, F. W. Wise and R. D. Robinson, *Nano Letters*, 2012, **12**, 5856-5860.
13. W. P. Lim, Z. Zhang, H. Y. Low and W. S. Chin, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 2004, **43**, 5685-5689.
14. H. Doh, S. Hwang and S. Kim, *Chemistry of Materials*, 2016, **28**, 8123-8127.
15. R. Ahmad, R. Srivastava, H. Bhardwaj, S. Yadav, V. Nand Singh, S. Chand, N. Singh and S. Sapra, *ChemistrySelect*, 2018, **3**, 5620-5629.
16. P. Jiang, C.-N. Zhu, Z.-L. Zhang, Z.-Q. Tian and D.-W. Pang, *Biomaterials*, 2012, **33**, 5130-5135.
17. Y. Wang and X.-P. Yan, *Chemical Communications*, 2013, **49**, 3324-3326.
18. I. Hocaoglu, M. N. Cizmeciyan, R. Erdem, C. Ozen, A. Kurt, A. Sennaroglu and H. Y. Acar, *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, 2012, **22**, 14674-14681.
19. T. Yang, Y. a. Tang, L. Liu, X. Lv, Q. Wang, H. Ke, Y. Deng, H. Yang, X. Yang, G. Liu, Y. Zhao and H. Chen, *ACS Nano*, 2017, **11**, 1848-1857.
20. L. Kong, W. Liu, X. Chu, Y. Yao, P. Zhu and X. Ling, *RSC Advances*, 2015, **5**, 80530-80535.
21. C. Wang, Y. Wang, L. Xu, D. Zhang, M. Liu, X. Li, H. Sun, Q. Lin and B. Yang, *Small*, 2012, **8**, 3137-3142.
22. A. Sahu, L. Qi, M. S. Kang, D. Deng and D. J. Norris, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2011, **133**, 6509-6512.
23. I. Hocaoglu, F. Demir, O. Birer, A. Kiraz, C. Sevrin, C. Grandfils and H. Yagci Acar, *Nanoscale*, 2014, **6**, 11921-11931.
24. R. Gui, A. Wan, X. Liu, W. Yuan and H. Jin, *Nanoscale*, 2014, **6**, 5467-5473.
25. Z. Zhuang, X. Lu, Q. Peng and Y. Li, *Chemistry – A European Journal*, 2011, **17**, 10445-10452.
26. G. Zhu and Z. Xu, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2011, **133**, 148-157.
27. Y. Wang, X. Li, M. Xu, K. Wang, H. Zhu, W. Zhao, J. Yan and Z. Zhang, *Nanoscale*, 2018, **10**, 2577-2587.
28. D. Asik, M. B. Yagci, F. Demir Duman and H. Yagci Acar, *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, 2016, **4**, 1941-1950.
29. X. Jia, D. Li, J. Li and E. Wang, *RSC Advances*, 2015, **5**, 80929-80932.
30. B. Ravel and M. Newville, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*, 2005, **12**, 537-541.
31. J. J. Rehr, J. J. Kas, F. D. Vila, M. P. Prange and K. Jorissen, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2010, **12**, 5503-5513.
32. I. G. Dance, K. J. Fisher, R. M. H. Banda and M. L. Scudder, *Inorganic Chemistry*, 1991, **30**, 183-187.